

Callus Production Protocol for *Andrographis paniculata*: A Valuable Medicinal Plant

Author's Details:

D.L.C.Kumari Fonseka,* and Dinesha Ranaweera

Department of Crop Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Ruhuna, Mapalana, Kamburupitiya, Sri Lanka *Corresponding author: kumarifonseka23@gmail.com

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Abstract

Andrographis paniculata is an important medicinal plant belongs to the family Acanthaceae possesses numerous valuable secondary metabolites. With the growing commercial importance for secondary metabolites has led to a great demand in the pharmaceutical industry in recent years. Therefore, an efficient callus production protocol was developed as a tool for extracting valuable secondary metabolites from *Andrographis paniculata*. Nodal cuttings, leaves and seeds were tested for surface sterilization with two Clorox® concentrations (10%, 15 %) and three exposure time periods (5 min, 10 min, 15 min). For callus induction and multiplication, the established cultures were transferred to Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with various combinations and concentrations of 1-Naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA) (1.0, 2.0 (mgL⁻¹)) and 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2, 4 D) (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 (mgL⁻¹)). Seeds were the most suitable explant for callus induction because of 100% non-contamination with all treatments. But for nodes and leaves, 0% non-contamination was observed ($P \leq 0.05$). When considering minimum resources allocation, 10% Clorox® for 5 minutes exposure time period was selected as the best surface sterilization method. Highest callus formation (91.8%) was observed in MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2, 4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA ($p \leq 0.05$). Result was significantly different only from the treatments with 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2, 4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA and 1.5 mgL⁻¹ 2, 4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA. Excellent callus with non-brownish colour (83%) and callus with excellent growth (67%) were observed in the same treatment. The optimized protocol could be used to produce higher amount of callus in order to extract secondary metabolites from *Andrographis paniculata*.

Keywords: *Andrographis paniculata*, Callus induction, medicinal plant, seed explants, secondary metabolites

INTRODUCTION

Andrographis paniculata is an important medicinal plant belongs to the family Acanthaceae with extensive uses in ayurvedic, unani and traditional medicine systems for centuries (Gaur *et al.*, 2018). The plant is commonly known as Heenbinkohomba or Kiratha in Sinhala and King of bitters in English due to its unique bitter taste. It is a herbaceous plant grows up to 75 cm tall which grows in Southern India, Sri Lanka, China, Thailand, and Pakistan.

Leaves and aerial parts of this plant are used in traditional medicine to treat various human ailments as they are rich in numerous secondary metabolites with medicinal properties. The most prominent active ingredient of *Andrographis paniculata* is Andrographolide which is bitter in taste (Hidalgo *et al.*, 2013). The plant has a wide range of pharmacological properties as Analgesic, Antibacterial, Antiperiodic, Antipyretic, Antithrombotic, Antiviral, Cancerolytic, Cardio protective, Thrombolytic, Laxative, Choleric, Digestive, Depurative, Expectorant, Hypoglycemic, Hepatoprotective and Immune enhancement (Bharati *et al.*, 2011; Kalaivaniet *al.*, 2012; Hidalgo *et al.*, 2013; Verma *et al.*, 2019; Gaur *et al.*, 2018;). Hence, it is used to treat various diseases ranging from cold and fever to hepatitis, bronchitis, kidney diseases and diabetes (Jayaweera and Senaratna, 1981).

Outsized production of material for extraction of secondary metabolites is the huge problem in this valuable species. Though *Andrographis paniculata* is conventionally propagated by seeds and vegetative means, there are some limitations such as low germination percentage of seeds, scanty of seeds, seed

dormancy, delayed rooting of seedlings and death of many young seedlings. Vegetative propagation of plant by stem cuttings is low in success. Due to unrestricted and unlimited exploitation to meet the growing demands by the pharmaceutical industries together with insufficient cultivation, this important medicinal plant has been faced the threat of eradication from their natural habitats. Therefore, fulfilling the growing demand in pharmaceutical industry for planting materials to the extraction of secondary metabolites has become challenging task.

In recent years, callus has been identified as a viable option for extraction of secondary metabolites from plant species. Secondary metabolite extraction from callus provides several advantages over other conventional plant parts as high speed of production, reduced space requirements, independency from climatic and seasonal variations and year-round production.

Hence, the aim of this study was to develop a suitable callus production protocol for *Andrographis paniculata* in order to extract valuable secondary metabolites. If the secondary metabolites produced in plant, could be extracted from callus will open up a new avenue in the pharmaceutical industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Nodes, leaves and mature pods of *Andrographis paniculata* were collected from healthy mother plants maintained in plant house conditions. Explants were first washed with a detergent under running tap water for 30 minutes. Later the Explants were dipped in a fungicide solution for 30 minutes, followed by washing with distilled water. Then the explants were tested for surface sterilization with two Clorox[®] concentrations (10%, 15 %) (v/v) and three exposure time periods (5 min, 10 min, 15 min) with continuous shaking and rinsed off with sterilized distilled water. Finally, it was treated with 70% ethyl alcohol for 30 seconds and washed off with sterilized distilled water. Explants were established in hormone free MS medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) to find out the contamination levels. All the cultures were maintained under illumination on a 16h photoperiod at 25 ± 2 °C.

MS medium supplemented with eight treatments of 2,4-D (0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 mgL⁻¹) and NAA (1.0 and 2.0 mgL⁻¹) were used to select best hormonal combination for callus induction and multiplication of *Andrographis paniculate*.

All experiments were arranged according to the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with 20 replicates. Non contamination percentage was observed to select the best surface sterilization procedure and suitable explant. Percentage of responded explants was observed to select the best condition for callus induction and quality of callus. Quality of callus was visually observed by using a scale for brownish and non-brownish callus and compact and fragile callus. In addition growth of callus was observed by visually by giving a score. Data were statistically analyzed and mean separation was done with DMRT (Duncan's Multiple Range Test). Non parametric data were analyzed using Kruskal-Wallis test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In most cases, the primary reason for failure of commercial tissue culture laboratories is the inability to control contaminations (Leifert and Woodward, 1998). Therefore, optimization of a suitable surface sterilization procedure for the explants plays a prominent role in success of the entire *in vitro* culture procedure of any species. When developing a callus production protocol for *Andrographis paniculate* for the secondary metabolite extraction, a proper surface sterilization procedure was optimized as the first step. Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) has been identified as a highly effective sterilant against most of the bacteria and fungi which cause contaminations in plant tissue culture (Yildiz, 2012). It is a practical selection as it can be easily diluted to the required concentration and readily available (Tiwari, Arya and Kumar, 2012). Clorox[®] bleach is a common sterilizing agent containing NaOCl as the main ingredient which has been used to sterilize many plant types (Daud, Jayaraman and Mohamed, 2012). In the current study explants were surface sterilized with two Clorox[®] concentrations (10%, 15 %) (v/v) and three exposure time periods (5 min, 10 min, 15 min) as the main sterilization procedure.

August 31, 2020

Table 1: Effect of Clorox® on different explants of *Andrographis paniculate*

Clorox® concentration (%)	Exposure time (min)	Non-contamination percentage (%)		
		Seeds	Nodal cuttings	Leaves
10	5	100	0	0
10	10	100	0	0
10	15	100	0	0
15	5	100	0	0
15	10	100	0	0
15	15	100	0	0

In nodal cuttings and leaves explants non-contamination percentages were recorded as zero while no contaminations were observed in seeds. Therefore, seeds were selected to continue the study while using 10% Clorox® for 5 minutes exposure time period, which was the most cost-effective treatment.

According to the literature Mercuric chloride has been used as the main surface sterilizing agent for various explants of *Andrographis paniculate*(Webster *et al.*, 2003). Seeds of *Andrographis paniculate* were recorded to be surface sterilized with 0.1% Mercuric chloride for 2 minutes, 3minutes and 10 minutes by Deshmukh *et al.*, (2017), Gandiet *al.*, (2012) and Tanweret *al.*, (2010) respectively. Young leaves of field grown *Andrographis paniculate* were surface sterilized with 0.1% Mercuric chloride for 10 minutes in another study (Praveen *et al.*, 2009) while Arifullahet *al.*, (2013) mentioned that leaf explants of *Andrographis paniculate* can be surface sterilized with 0.1% Mercuric chloride for 2 minutes. Though Mercuric chloride considered as a superior surface sterilant in *in vitro* culturing, it has serious threats towards humans and environment alike. Hence, an efficient alternative is crucial and Clorox® has proven to be a successful solution according to the current study.

Plant growth regulators play an important role in production of higher amount of high-quality callus. Auxins induce callus formation and proliferation while 2,4 D can be identified as the most efficient plant growth regulator related to callus culture (Luciani *et al.*, 2006). Different concentrations and combinations of 2,4 D and NAA were tested for the callus induction from seed explants of *Andrographis paniculate* in the current study.

Though contaminations occurred rarely, seeds established with seed coat did not produce callus even after five weeks from culture initiation. Hence, seeds were split in to two halves using forceps before establishing in the culture medium. Extreme care was taken at this step as seeds of *Andrographis paniculate* are miniature and delicate. Callus production was observed in the seeds established after this treatment. Therefore, seed cultures of *Andrographis paniculate* should be established after splitting for a better callus induction.

Figure 1: Effect of different combinations and concentrations of 2, 4 D and NAA on callus induction of *Andrographis paniculate* seed explants.

August 31, 2020

Highest callus induction percentage (91.8%) was observed in the treatments with 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA and 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA (Figure 1). The value was significantly different only from treatments with 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA (47.6%) and 1.5 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA (20%).

In previous studies it has been found that maximum callusing frequency can be obtained in 2,4-D combined with NAA (Pawaret *et al.*, 2018). According to Vidyalakshmi and Ananthi (2013), MS medium supplemented with 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4D and 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA was found to be the best medium for callus induction from *Andrographis paniculate*. In another study best response for callus initiation was observed on MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 0.4 mgL⁻¹ BAP from seed explants of *Andrographis paniculate* (Gandiet *et al.*, 2012). Current study proves that, MS medium supplemented with 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA or 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA also can be used for the successful callus induction of *Andrographis paniculate* seed explants.

Effect of 2,4D and NAA on quality and quantity of callus were measured by observing the appearance of callus according to the colour and growth. Seed explants were highly responded to callusing in some treatments and callus formation was started after three weeks from establishment. Initially white colour callus was formed and then it was gradually turned into creamy white colour (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Quality and growth of callus under different combinations and concentrations of 2, 4 D and NAA; a: 0.5 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA; b: 0.5 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA; c: 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA; d: 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA; e: 1.5 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA; f: 1.5 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA; g: 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA; h: 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA

Callus produced under each treatment was evaluated and categorized as excellent, good and poor according to visual observations. Percentage of calli with excellent quality and growth were calculated to identify the best level of 2,4 D and NAA.

August 31, 2020

Figure 3: Percentage of callus with excellent quality and growth produced under different combinations and concentrations of 2, 4 D and NAA.

Highest percentages of callus with excellent quality and growth were observed in MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA which was significantly different from all other treatments. MS medium supplemented with 1.5 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D + 2.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA did not produce callus with excellent quality or excellent growth.

In previous callus culture studies, use of 2,4 D together with some other plant growth regulators has been recorded in many occasions for the callus induction of *Andrographis paniculate*. In most cases callus has been proliferated in the same medium used for callus induction. Maximum amount of callus was obtained from seed explants of *Andrographis paniculate* in MS medium supplemented with 4.52 µM 2,4 D and 5.71 µM IAA according to Tanwer *et al.*, (2010). Better quality callus was obtained from *in vitro* grown leaf explants of *Andrographis paniculate* in MS medium supplemented with 1.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D and 1.0 mgL⁻¹ Kinetin in another study (Deshmukh *et al.*, 2017). MS medium supplemented with 4.52 µM 2,4 D and 2.22 µM BA reported to produce highest amount of callus from leaf and internode explants of *Andrographis paniculate* (Martin, 2004). Current study proved that MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D and 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA also can be used to produce higher amount of high-quality callus from seed explants of *Andrographis paniculate*.

CONCLUSION

According to the results of current study, it can be concluded that callus can be produced successfully from seed explants of *Andrographis paniculate* as a tool for the secondary metabolite extraction. Seeds should be split in to two halves before culture initiation for a higher response of callus induction. 10% Clorox[®] for 5 minutes exposure time period can be used as the most economic surface sterilization method. MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mgL⁻¹ 2,4 D and 1.0 mgL⁻¹ NAA can be used for callus induction as well as callus multiplication as it produced higher amount of high-quality callus. The optimized protocol can be used for commercial purposes as well as further studies.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None

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August 31, 2020

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